

Pathogenesis and Immune Evasion Strategies of Influenza A Virus: Challenges for Therapeutic Innovation

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Abstract:

Influenza From the Orthomyxoviridae family, a virus (IAV) is a highly adaptive pathogen that affects a variety of avian and mammalian hosts, including humans. Its rapidly evolving segmented RNA genome makes it easier for immune evasion and the generation of novel subtypes, including those that cause pandemics. The virological features of IAV are examined in this study, with particular attention paid to the roles that neuraminidase (NA) and haemagglutinin (HA) play in infection. The discussion of IAV pathogenesis in relation to respiratory tract infections emphasizes the virus's capacity to compromise endothelium and epithelial barriers, resulting in serious difficulties for the lungs. We look closely

at the immune evasion tactics used by IAV, such as blocking the host's interferon response via non-structural protein 1 (NS1). The study also discusses the continuous difficulties in therapeutic innovation, highlighting the necessity of developing new antiviral tactics to combat the virus's fast rates of mutation and increasing resistance to current therapies. Gaining an understanding of these pathways is essential to creating efficient treatments for pandemic and seasonal strains alike.

Keywords: *Influenza A virus (IAV), Viral pathogenesis, Immune evasion, Pulmonary complications, Therapeutic innovation.*

Abbreviations: IAV: Influenza A Virus; NA: Neuraminidase; HA: Hemagglutinin; RNP: Ribonucleoprotein; ENaC: Epithelial Sodium Channel; NS1: Non-Structural Protein 1; IFN: Interferon; SOCS: Suppressor of Cytokine Signaling; PKR: Protein Kinase R; HPAI: Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza; TIV: Trivalent Inactivated Vaccine; LAIV: Live Attenuated Influenza Vaccine.

Introduction

Influenza IAVs are members of the Orthomyxoviridae virus family (Palese and Shaw, 2007 reviewed). The surface antigens neuraminidase (NA or N) and haemagglutinin (HA or H) are used to subtype them. Nine kinds of NA and sixteen subtypes of HA have been identified in birds thus far, which are the host species for most IAV strains. IAVs are distinguished by an RNA genome that is segmented and arranged into eight ribonucleoprotein (RNP) units per virion, each of which can encode up to eleven different proteins (Schmolke, & García-Sastre, 2010). Influenza A Invasive animal viruses, or IAVs, are significant diseases that affect both human and veterinary health globally. Many different types of birds and mammals are among the many host species that fall under this broad group of viruses. Influenza's ecology and epidemiology A virus may infect a variety of free-living, domesticated, and captive-raised birds in addition to a wide range of wild and domesticated mammals in a variety of settings, such as humans, pigs, horses, dogs, and bats. It can also occasionally infect a variety of other mammalian hosts (Suarez, 2016). Human infections with the seasonal influenza virus occur in yearly epidemics that affect millions of people globally and have a major negative impact on both health and the economy (Medina, & García-Sastre, 2011). Globally, influenza viruses pose a serious hazard to human health through their infections. Vaccines and antiviral drugs can both prevent and cure the disease, but they are not widely available and have a subpar level of effectiveness (Julkunen, et al., 2001).

Virological background of Influenza A

Among all human viruses, influenza A has two distinct epidemiological mechanisms. The virus has periodically, but regularly, evolved into a whole new subtype with a new group of genes, mainly those encoding for neuraminidase (NA) and haemagglutinin (HA). Although the source

of these emerging influenzas is unknown, they are thought to have originated from the same pandemic mode that, in recent memory, resulted in global pandemics in 1889, 1898, 1918, 1957, 1968, and 1977 (Stuart-Harris, et al., 1985). The first H1N1 case was recorded on May 13, 2009, in Hyderabad, a city in southern India. Between that date and May 11, 2010, 31 837 laboratories confirmed H1N1 infections were reported. The first fatality from a verified case of H1N1 occurred on 3 August 2009, and from then to 11 May 2010 a total of 1511 fatalities were recorded (Bal, et al., 2012). Constant point mutations in the influenza virus cause significant alterations in antigenic regions, which aid in the virus's slow evolution by causing antigen movement and the emergence of new influenza virus subtypes that evade the population's immune system (Shao, et al., 2017). Seasonal influenza is a recurrent threat to human health, largely because it rapidly accumulates. amino-acid mutations in proteins targeted by the immune system (Doud, & Bloom, 2016).

Pathogenesis of Influenza A Virus

Studies using avian influenza A viruses have yielded most of the information currently known regarding highly pathogenic influenza viruses. Knowledge about avian influenza is pertinent to human illness as, as the pandemic strains of 1957 and 1968 demonstrated, the avian population is likely the source of human pandemic strains, and several viruses known to be harmful in birds may also function in humans (Zambon, 2001). Influenza A virus is a respiratory infection that has a significant global impact on human health. Every year, epidemics caused by seasonal viruses that are circulating in the human population result in around 500,000 deaths.¹ A new strain of the influenza A worldwide pandemic with varying fatality might be created by a virus that does not already have immunity in the population; in the first year of its transmission, the 2009 H1N1 pandemic claimed between 151,700 and 575,400 lives (Short, et al., 2014). Influenza A virus primarily binds the respiratory epithelium. Subsequent infection of epithelial

cells can lead to pulmonary edema by interfering with epithelial sodium channel (ENaC) function, an important mediator of alveolar fluid clearance. (Stuart-Harris, et al., 1985; Bal, et al., 2012; Shao, et al., 2017). However, endothelial dysfunction is thought to be the main factor involved in the development of pulmonary edema (Doud, & Bloom, 2016). Thus, understanding how the influenza virus causes disruption of the endothelial barrier is critical

(Kuiken, Taubenberger, & Fouchier, 2010). Only a few strains or lineages of influenza A virus are classified as select agents: first, all HPAI viruses, as regulated by US Department of Agriculture; second, reverse genetic constructs containing all 8 gene segments of the 1918 H1N1 Spanish influenza virus, as regulated by US Department of Health and Human Services (Van Reeth, 2000).

Figure 1. The host range of influenza A virus. Notes: The IAV HA subtypes isolated from each host are mentioned in parenthesis. The significant interspecies IAV transmission is shown by solid (common) and dashed (sporadic) arrows
Abbreviations: IAV, influenza A virus; HA, hemagglutinin.

Immune Evasion Strategies of Influenza A Virus

influenza A virus (IAV) remains an important human pathogen, largely because of its ability to evade the humoral immune response. Immune evasion is primarily based on the protean capacity of the HA glycoprotein to accommodate amino acid substitutions that modify antigenicity and modulate receptor avidity. HA is a homotrimer that attaches virus to terminal sialic acid residues on target cells to initiate the infectious cycle. Antibodies (Abs)

that interact with the globular HA domain sterically block attachment and neutralize viral infectivity (Sebina, & Pepper, 2018). Viral metamorphosis is the way by which the innate immune response is evaded; in particular, the viral nonstructural proteins (NS1) take on several forms to agitate the innate defense against the virus. Viral NS1 proteins suppress the retinoic acid-inducible gene I (RIG-I) receptors, which function as sensors for viral recognition. As a result, the RIG-I mediated detection of the virus's 5'-phosphorylated

ssRNA is impeded (Naveed, Abdullah, & Naveed, 2019). Proteins from the influenza virus have the ability to attach to and inhibit several innate immune system components. The rapid pace of influenza viral genome mutation in humans combined with immunological pressure results in the emergence of antigenically different influenza viruses that are either completely or only partially recognized by the current adaptive humoral and cellular immune repertoire (Kreijtz, Fouchier, & Rimmelzwaan, 2011). As the most significant IFN-antagonist protein expressed by the virus, the non-structural protein of influenza virus NS1 has developed several strategies to reduce the IFN response during influenza virus infection. This protein may interact with many IFN response components and suppress them, which is why it is highly produced in the cytoplasm and nucleus of infected cells (García-Sastre, 2011). To confront or evade the innate immune system, the influenza viruses also take advantage of specific cellular regulators to inhibit the antiviral effects

of the type I IFNs. It has been observed that influenza virus-induced suppressor of cytokine signaling (SOCS) factors inhibit the type I IFNs signaling. Influenza viruses also utilize the cellular PKR inhibitor P58(IPK) to interfere PKR activation through dissociation the P58(IPK) from Hsp40 and minimizes the antiviral state of cell (Das, Hensley, & Yewdell, 2011). generally The mechanisms by which IAV NS1 modulates the cellular machinery to promote viral replication include such a wide range of pathways that highlights its relevance as a multifunctional virulence factor. Because of the intrinsic mutational rate of IAV during replication and its ability to infect different hosts, NS1 is in constant evolutionary pressure. Our recent research efforts have analyzed the NS1 evolutionary landscape and host tropism using a barcoded NS1 library of recombinant NS1 IAV, providing new insights on the plasticity of the protein and its ability to adapt to different hosts (Muñoz-Moreno, Martínez-Romero, & García-Sastre, 2021).

Figure 2. Strategies used by viruses to evade infection and bystander cells. (A) IAV NS1 interferes with TRIM25 to inhibit RIG-I activation. (B) The IAV polymerase complex's grabbing of the 5'-m7G-cap and NS1's interference with CPSF30 cause the host protein synthesis to stop. (C) In host cells, SOCS3 upregulation inhibits IFN type I signaling. (D) ISGs are directly agitated by IAV NS1

Challenges in Therapeutic Innovation

Influenza viruses continue to change their antigenicity by successfully evading the host immunity to infections. The antigenic drift caused by genetic mutations in the influenza viral genome not only leads to the emergence of drug resistant strains (Tozzi, Adorisio, & Gabrieli, 2024). Deeper understanding of the structures and activities of viral components is of great interest as it relates to the development of novel medications to combat resistance and the possibility of occasional outbreaks of viruses with pandemic potential. The body of knowledge resulting from fresh research projects could someday be transformed into practical treatment plans (Loregian, et al., 2014). Basic drug design and screening platforms are needed to speed up the drug discovery process against both new and pre-existing targets that have drug resistance issues. Each approach will be briefly

covered in this part with regard to the search for anti-influenza drugs. Zanamivir, which continues to garner a lot of interest because of its remarkable antiviral activity against both wild-type and oseltamivir-resistant strains, is one of the most successful instances of pharmacophore-based drug development. Hydrophobic centroids, aromatic rings, hydrogen bond acceptors or donors, cations, and anions are all features of pharmacophore modeling. These can be established through two methods: structure-based modeling, which uses the target protein's pre-defined three-dimensional (3D) structure, or ligand-based modeling, which uses active ligand information. Combining the pharmacophore characteristics of putative ligands with the target protein, assuming the 3D structure is known, helps discover more selective hits (Shin, & Seong, 2013).

Figure 3. Key influenza vaccines based on eggs and their sales and market shares. Fluvirin made for just \$2 million of Chiron's flu vaccine sales in 2004. * Flu Mist revenues were not recognized by Medimmune in 2003. Based on a \$1.3 billion overall market value; Flu vac was initially introduced as a whole virus vaccine in the 1950s and changed to a subunit vaccine in 1983; Sales for 2004 are estimated, however sales for the 2003 flu virus are not predicted. Vaccines against influenza that are trivalent inactivated (TIVs) and live attenuated (LAIVs) are available

By analyzing the interactions between inhibitors and the protein in the enzyme-binding pocket (Short, et al., 2014), recent developments in pharmacophore modeling and structural biology have produced new and effective influenza medications (Sabbaghi, et al., 2020; Yang, Bukhari, & Wei, 2022; Das, Hensley, & Yewdell, 2011; Muñoz-Moreno, Martínez-Romero, & García-Sastre, 2021). Understanding a receptor's binding pocket for its ligand is crucial for drug design, especially when performing mutagenesis research. According to published definitions, a protein receptor's binding pocket is often described in the literature as residues with at least one heavy atom located five atoms away from a ligand's heavy atom. The Cdk5-Nck5a* complex's ATP binding pocket was first defined using this criterion, which subsequently proved to be highly helpful in determining the functional domains and inciting the pertinent truncation studies. Definitions of binding pockets for several additional receptor-ligand interactions that are significant for drug design have been made using a methodology akin to this (Sabbaghi, et al., 2020). On the other hand, Epidemiological trends are caused by antigenic drift of influenza A and B strains, whereas antigenic shift of the A strain can start a pandemic³ if the newly reconstituted virus has a high case fatality rate and strong human-to-human transmissibility. A pandemic may impact 25–35% of the population and cost an estimated \$550 billion, but an epidemic's economic cost is estimated to be \$12 billion. This information comes from the World Bank (Yang, Bukhari, & Wei, 2022).

Discussion

Influenza A virus's (IAV) quick adaptation and capacity to elude immune responses pose serious threats to world health. Because of the RNA genome's segmentation, antigenic shifts and drifts can occur often, allowing IAV to continuously change its antigenic characteristics and evade immune monitoring. The virus's ability to infect a variety of host species contributes to its capability for adaptability and

creates a large reservoir for possible zoonotic transmission (Wang, Pianko, & Ke, 2011).

IAV's tactics for thwarting the immune system, especially the use of the non-structural protein 1 (NS1), highlight the virus's adaptability. NS1 has the ability to obstruct host interferon signaling pathways, which are essential for antiviral defense and allow viruses to replicate and spread within the host. Furthermore, by developing a defense against detection by neutralizing antibodies, HA and NA surface proteins not only aid in infection but also immunological escape (Smith, et al., 1997). The creation of efficient antiviral treatments is hampered by these evasion strategies. Although neuraminidase inhibitors like as oseltamivir and zanamivir have demonstrated their efficacy, the virus's capacity to evolve resistance highlights the necessity for innovative treatment methodologies. The current state of research on immune modulators and host-targeted therapeutics is promising, but the fast rate of IAV mutation calls for ongoing innovation in therapeutic approaches (Iannello, et al., 2006).

Conclusion

Influenza A virus (IAV) has the potential to rapidly evolve genetically and can infect a broad variety of hosts, making it a serious danger to world health. Because of its segmented RNA genome, antigenic drift and the generation of new, drug-resistant strains are facilitated by frequent mutations. IAV's high pathogenicity is highlighted by its capacity to damage respiratory epithelial and endothelial barriers, resulting in serious pulmonary consequences. In addition, the virus successfully eludes both innate and adaptive immune responses, with NS1, or non-structural protein 1, being a key player in blocking interferon signaling. The development of vaccines and therapeutic therapies continues to face difficulties because to these immune evasion tactics and the fast mutation rates of IAV. The ability of the virus to evolve resistance compromises the effectiveness of current antiviral medicines, notwithstanding their

relative effectiveness. Innovative treatment strategies that can target the virus and its immune evasion mechanisms are therefore desperately needed. In order to create more potent therapies that can combat both seasonal outbreaks and possible pandemics, more investigation into the structure, pathophysiology, and immune evasion tactics of IAV is essential.

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